

Supplemental Figure 1. Ciliary localization of Smo induced by SAG. MEF cells were treated with either DMSO (control) or the Hedgehog agonist SAG (50 nM, 200 nM). Cells were co-immunolabelled with antibodies against Smo and the cilia marker Arl13B to examine Smo localization in the primary cilium.